

Impact of Rajyoga Meditation on Mental Health Among Secondary School Students

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Abstract

Mental health issues among secondary school students have become a growing concern worldwide due to increasing academic pressure, social challenges and emotional instability during adolescence. This review paper explores the impact of Rajyoga meditation on the mental health of secondary school students. Rajyoga meditation, a simple and accessible mind–body practice, has been recognized for its potential psychological and emotional benefits. The paper analyzes existing literature related to meditation practices and their effects on stress, anxiety, emotional regulation and cognitive functioning. Findings from various studies indicate that Rajyoga meditation contributes to reduced stress levels, improved emotional stability, enhanced concentration and better overall mental well-being. However, there is limited research specifically focusing on secondary school students. The review highlights the need for further research and suggests integrating meditation practices into school systems to promote students' mental health and academic performance.

Keywords: Rajyoga Meditation, Mental Health, Secondary School Students, Stress, Anxiety, Emotional Well-being.

1. Introduction

Adolescents is a crucial stage of life characterized by rapid physical, emotional and psychological changes. Secondary school students often face various challenges such as academic pressure, peer influence, family expectations and social stress. These factors can significantly affect their mental health, leading to issues such as anxiety, depression and emotional instability (Patel, Flisher, Hetrick, & McGorry, 2007).

In recent years, mental health problems among adolescents have increased globally, making it an important area of concern for educators and policy makers. Studies indicate that academic pressure and life style factors contribute significantly to stress among school students (Zenner et al.,2014). If not addressed properly, these issues can negatively impact students' academic performance and overall well-being.

Among Various meditation practices have been associated with physiological and psychological benefits, including reduced stress levels, improved mood and enhanced cognitive functioning (Tang at al.,2015). These benefits are particularly relevant for secondary school students, who are at a sensitive stage of development.

1.1. Nature of Rajyoga Meditation

Rajyoga meditation is a cognitive and awareness-based meditative practice that emphasizes self-regulation, positive thinking and mental discipline. It involves directing attention inward and developing awareness of one's thoughts, emotions and mental processes. Unlike physically intensive forms of yoga, Rajyoga meditation focuses primarily on mental and psychological aspects of self-control.

This practice has been associated with improved emotional regulation and stress management. By cultivating awareness and cognitive control, individuals can reduce negative thought patterns and enhance psychological resilience. Regular practice is linked to improved concentration, attention and decision-making abilities, which are important for students in academic settings (Tang et al., 2015).